

CHANGES IN THE ORAL CAVITY IN TUBERCULOSIS

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Annotation: In this article, the presence of an odontogenic focus in patients with respiratory tuberculosis is a characteristic sign of intoxication of the disease process, changes in blood, lung erosion, processes of changes in immunoglobulins and immune components, the respiratory system itself provides. special features. dental care in the treatment of patients

Key words: tuberculosis of the respiratory system, stomatology, oral cavity, caries, tooth, treatment.

Tuberculosis is the second leading cause of death from any infectious disease, second only to HIV/AIDS. In 2013, 9 million people were infected with tuberculosis and 1.5 million people died from this disease¹. In addition, more and more people in developed countries are getting TB because their immune systems are weakened by taking immunosuppressive drugs, heavy drug use, and especially HIV infection. Tuberculosis is often accompanied by HIV infection. According to most scientists, tuberculosis is detected in 17.8% of HIV-infected patients and resistance to antibiotics is observed in 25% of cases, which makes the problem of tuberculosis very relevant, especially for dentists. The presence of an odontogenic focus in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis is characterized by specific intoxication symptoms of the disease process, changes in the blood, lung erosion, changes in immunoglobulins and immune components. When the odontogenic focus is eliminated, the indicators of the immune system and the clinical course of the disease are improved.

At the same time, the importance of pathogenetic methods of treatment, including the correction of dental pathology, increases. One of the factors that help to improve the effectiveness of tuberculosis treatment is good nutrition, which depends not only on the content of food, but also on the quality of its processing in the oral cavity.

Dental care for patients with lung disease is very important because the oral cavity becomes a gateway for infection. Medical professionals, including dentists, are becoming increasingly aware of the need for measures to prevent patient-to-staff transmission, as well as to prevent the spread of infection in a medical facility. Patients with weak immunity (those suffering from general somatic diseases; those undergoing radiation and chemotherapy; those listed in drug, oncological, anti-tuberculosis dispensaries) are increasingly being seen by dentists. However, such patients are at risk of infection and susceptibility to it. Therefore, the doctor should consider each patient as a carrier of the infection and take all measures to prevent its spread.

Treatment measures:

¹Abdukhakimov B. A. The effect of anti-tuberculosis treatment measures on the functional state of the thyroid gland //Journal cardiorespiratoryx issledovaniy. - 2020.

The most effective medicinal plants for rinsing the oral cavity include: chamomile, calendula, calanchoe. Among the drugs, chlorhexidine, anesthesin solutions and glycerin, vitamin A oil concentrate were recommended for local application and rinsing. After the antiseptic stages of treatment, if there are wounds on the gums and the entire oral surface, epithelization-accelerating agents are used, including vitamins A, D, Ayevit drug, Solcoseryl, vegetable oils, Kuriozan-gel ointment. To describe the condition of the teeth, the value of the index (KPU) consisting of the sum of the teeth with caries, filled and removed, as well as individual cases of complicated and uncomplicated caries is determined. When evaluating the results of dental treatment, taking into account that tuberculosis is the main disease, we can summarize the effectiveness of the developed principles and the proposed treatment principles, but it should be remembered that in addition to the elimination of local negative factors and the treatment of tuberculosis, these patients should also be monitored dynamically demands to go.

Along with the positive effects of complex treatment, one should not forget the social impact. It should be aimed at improving the psycho-emotional and general condition of patients, reducing pain and, most importantly, improving the quality of life of patients in combination with comprehensive and targeted treatment of the main diseases based on the use of modern approaches and treatment methods. If problems in the oral cavity are observed in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis, the general treatment of patients should be supplemented with local dental treatment, including oral hygiene. It should also be noted that when the symptoms of depression caused by the general state of the body of patients with pulmonary tuberculosis, as well as the side effects of antibacterial drugs, are often combined with the state of psychosis, the attending physician in cooperation with the neuropathologist prescribes sedative drugs to the patient. should also be recommended. Improving the composition and order of nutrition, emotional state, quality of work and life of patients with pulmonary tuberculosis helps to increase the effectiveness of treatment.

Conclusion: The results of the study showed that tuberculosis of the oral cavity and the entire dentition system is considered to be a manifestation of tuberculosis infection of the general organism, therefore, the treatment should be carried out comprehensively, taking into account the general condition of the patient. should continue with hygienic, therapeutic and other measures. Treating doctors in cooperation with dentists should treat the whole body of patients with pulmonary tuberculosis. The dentist, on the other hand, is responsible for the tactics of treatment of the oral cavity, that is, the elimination of foci of odontogenic infection, the use of anti-inflammatory therapy in pathology, the tissues surrounding the teeth, should deal with treatment measures such as treatment of damaged surfaces of the cavity and various parts of the mucous membrane of the lips, restoration of defects in dental prosthesis.

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